

Thoughts of Mahatma Gandhi on Trusteeship

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There is economic inequality and exploitation everywhere in the society and because of this class idolatry continues in the society, Mahatma Gandhi proposed the theory of Trusteeship. It made life more pleasant, so that cooperation among human beings can be properly evaluated, its place in the social life, but seeing that in this sense, human society created inequality and gave rise to exploitation, many social reformers and noble men suggested different measures to create equality. In the society, due to which Equality will be created in the Indian society, everyone will get a chance to achieve their development, but there has been no success in this effort in India, even if inequality remains in the society, the social system has been created.

The society is divided to the extent that the backward class will remain. Since ancient times, efforts have been made to eliminate this inequality, but it has not been so successful. Similarly, he proposed the theory that the nation has a right to the wealth that he should live with dignity and it should be used for the national interest. The above trustee is an important concept in Gandhi an economy. He expected that people should not use it for their own consumption. Man should keep his needs to a minimum. The rich should not claim the wealth that is more than the wealth needed to live with dignity. The society should own the wealth and that wealth should be used only for the welfare of the society. According to the idea that if the idea is implemented, the economic disparity in the society will be destroyed. Mahatma Gandhi believed that an economy based on economic equality will be created by giving up the ownership rights of the factory and the workers will become trustees along with the owner.

Concept of Trusteeship

The concept of trusteeship is mentioned as an important concept while studying the administrative thought of Mahatma Gandhi. Mahatma Gandhi's ideological philosophy is referred to as 'Gandhi's'. Of this Gandhi's. The concepts of 'truth, non-violence, self-reliance and trust' are mentioned as the four main bases. Gandhi adopted all these four principles in his mantle only after that he made these principles'

constitutional and public'. Gandhi's thoughts were based on 'humanism and moral values. The concept of trust proposed by him also depends on these considerations. For that we have to review this concept in detail.

Emergence and Background of Trust Concept

According to Marathi Encyclopedia the concept of trustee originated from 'Puritan religion' (a devout Christian community). The concept of trust is considered important in Mahatma Gandhi's economic thought. Gandhi thought of trustee concept in South Africa in AD. It was presented in 1903. After that further AD In his book "Hindswarajya" in 1909, he embodied the concept of trusteeship. On the occasion of the inauguration of Banaras Hindu University in 1916, he challenged all the institutions in the country to use their wealth as trustees for public welfare. This is what Gandhi first said in 1916. Through his speech, he carefully presented the concept of trust.

What is the theory of Trusteeship?

The concept of trusteeship holds that individuals and businesses should not store their wealth and resources for their own benefit. Also this theory states that wealth should not be used for exploitation.

On the contrary, Gandhi suggests that wealth should be used for the wider welfare of the society. Gandhi insisted that individuals or companies who have wealth, capital should use it for the welfare of the society instead of profiteering.

A sense of moral responsibility

At the core of trusteeship is the idea that wealth should be used to address social inequality and promote social justice. Gandhi argued that the concentration of wealth in the hands of a few was detrimental to the welfare of society and that the wealthy had a duty to voluntarily redistribute their resources for the upliftment of the disadvantaged.

This concept is compatible with the principles of wealth redistribution and income taxation. After independence, India adopted a mixed economy and adopted Gandhi's concept to some extent. Although Gandhi was against profiteering, he was not against the capitalist system. Therefore, a distinction can be made between Marxist economic thought and Gandhian economic thought. Gandhi concept of trusteeship can be considered through the following means when the capitalist system is growing strongly in today's time.

Who accepted the concept of trusteeship?

Gandhi said that the product produced by any company is owned not only by the owner of the company but also by the society. Gandhi also convinced the then industrialists of his economic views. Sir Ratan Tata, G.D. Businessmen like Birla and Jamnalal Bajaj adopted Gandhi's economic philosophy.

All these three industrialists contributed their best to the Indian freedom struggle and used most of the profits for the betterment of the society. It is important to note here that Gandhi's concept of trusteeship does not at all advocate the abolition of private property or the rejection of capitalism. That is why industrialists Tata, Birla and Bajaj sided with Gandhi. He chose to do business ethically and responsibly with wealth and resources. Although the practical implementation of trusteeship varies, its basic principles guide the creation of a fairer and more balanced financial system.

Key principles of fiduciary concept

We can tell the nature of the trust concept proposed by Mahatma Gandhi through the following key principles. Mahatma Gandhi's concept of trust is mainly based on these principles.

➤ **Principle of creation of economic equality**

Mahatma Gandhi is of the opinion that many problems in society arise from economic inequality. Therefore, an ideal and good society has to be created by creating economic equality. Gandhi goes on to say that the fiduciary concept is useful for creating economic equality through humanism and moral values without resorting to violent means.

➤ **Principle of Exploitation**

Mahatma Gandhi considered the trust concept as a tool for emancipation from exploitation. Mahatma Gandhi said that every person in the society should use what they have instead of consuming it according to their needs because when consumption is more than the need then the level of exploitation increases in the society. If more and more goods are used according to need instead of consumption, exploitation free society will be created

➤ **Principle of socialist society building**

Mahatma Gandhi said that when wealth is concentrated in society, capitalism is created. When capitalism is created, rich-poor, class conflict, unemployment increases. Mahatma Gandhi is of the opinion that if we want to avoid the dependence of violent ways in the society, the trustee concept is important because this is what creates a socialist society structure.

➤ **Principles of Humanism and Ethics**

In Trust Concept, Gandhi gave high moral conduct and gave importance to humanitarian ideas. Emphasize.

➤ **Principle of sense of responsibility**

Gandhi says that whatever is more in your wealth, power and intelligence should be used for the society. Every person should be responsible towards society and nature.

➤ **Principle of heart transformation**

Gandhi says that it depends on the fulfillment of a person's dreams, the wealth that we have is not the only owner, but that wealth belongs to the society and that wealth should be used for the welfare of the society.

➤ **Principle of human self-respect**

Gandhi says that trustee concept is not an instrument of loot if the concept of benevolence or loot arises in this concept then this concept will be destroyed similarly in trustee concept it is not expected to help the healthy persons the whole concept depends on the principle of human self-respect.

➤ **Importance of Social and Legal Remedial Schemes**

Mahatma Gandhi says that if the rich class is not ready to act with a sense of trust, the common people should use non-violent and constructive means to pressure them and adopt a policy of non-cooperation. And also explains the principle of legal remedy schemes.

Conclusion

Mahatma Gandhi's concept of trusteeship is a very important concept, especially in order to promote different businesses including small scale industries, this concept of Mahatma Gandhi is very important from the point of view of self-development of the economy in the rural areas. Have or have money they should spend it for the society mainly through the concept of trustees Mahatma Gandhi proposed this concept for how to approach inclusive development. In modern times the concept of development is not seen as sustainable development mainly considering the rural areas but the concept of Trustee proposed by Mahatma Gandhi is mainly leading to sustainable development. Mahatma Gandhi says that expenditure for factors outside of development is also important because unless we do comprehensive development of the rural areas, the country cannot develop in the true sense, so for a developed country we need the concept of sustainable development and at the same time the concept of trusteeship is also important.